

Opinion: Big Bang is not a Real Cosmology

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This paper best viewed at <https://bit.ly/3acM9Sy>

Synopsis: The Big Bang Theory, temporarily renamed Expansion Theory then renewed (probably because of the propaganda power of the TV show) as Big Bang (BB), is not a true cosmology. The only way that it works as a cosmology is when rolled up and bundled with other aspects, such as incompatible Black Hole Theory, Quantum Mechanics, General Relativity, and debunkable ideas such as wave-particle duality¹ and neutron stars², and most especially with Dark Matter and Dark Energy. In this bundle, or smattering of scientific and pseudoscientific theories we call the Standard Model (SM). However, most of these theories have little to nothing to do with each other in historical development, and many of them are completely contradictory to one another. When plasma or condensed matter (such as Liquid Metallic Hydrogen, or crystal plasma, or Bose-Einstein Condensates) are included, they are utilized as matters of scientific facts as if in support, but never given prominence (since Gravity is the primary force astronomers obsess over, wrongly).

However, real cosmologies are inclusive of all that we see, with all of the data we are given. Cosmogony, mythology, archaeology, physics, astronomy and astrology, etc. all relate directly to the true formation of a real cosmology. Big Bang does not survive intense scrutiny within itself, as there exist multiple debunkings of it on dozens of lines of evidence, nor does it make for a real cosmogony, nor obey mythos descriptions. It does have a Judeo-Christian background, to Genesis, but otherwise is not capable of really explaining what is seen and besides as we delve into Sumer, Babylon, and Gobekli Tepe (and also now the Amazon), we see that it doesn't match mythological records of the cosmos, either. Particularly Accretion fails, and this describes why we do not find any AM computer simulations which work well to describe the idiosyncrasies of our Solar System.

Keywords: Big-Bang, Black Holes, Einstein, Gravity, Plasma, Electromagnetism, Cosmology

¹ Light is demonstrably not a particle but a wave that behaves digitally.

² A fun hypothesis involving insane rotations of a "fundamental" particle that has no incentive to adhere to each other (we know this from atomic experiments. Also the rotational speeds would destroy them. It is a bad hypothesis to explain pulsars, which are more easily explained with the Eric Lerner plasma pulsing theorem.

Background

The History of Creation

1In the beginning God created the heavens and the earth. **2**The earth was without form, and void; and darkness [a]was on the face of the deep. And the Spirit of God was hovering over the face of the waters.

3Then God said, "Let there be light"; and there was light. **4**And God saw the light, that *it was good*; and God divided the light from the darkness. **5**God called the light Day, and the darkness He called Night. [b]So the evening and the morning were the first day.

6Then God said, "Let there be a [c]firmament in the midst of the waters, and let it divide the waters from the waters." **7**Thus God made the firmament, and divided the waters which were under the firmament from the waters which were above the firmament; and it was so. **8**And God called the firmament Heaven. So the evening and the morning were the second day.

9Then God said, "Let the waters under the heavens be gathered together into one place, and let the dry *land* appear"; and it was so. **10**And God called the dry *land* Earth, and the gathering together of the waters He called Seas. And God saw that *it was good*.

11Then God said, "Let the earth bring forth grass, the herb *that yields seed*, and the fruit tree *that yields fruit according to its kind*, whose seed *is* in itself, on the earth"; and it was so. **12**And the earth brought forth grass, the herb *that yields seed according to its kind*, and the tree *that yields fruit*, whose seed *is* in itself according to its kind. And God saw that *it was good*. **13**So the evening and the morning were the third day.

14Then God said, "Let there be lights in the firmament of the heavens to divide the day from the night; and let them be for signs and seasons, and for days and years; **15**and let them be for lights in the firmament of the heavens to give light on the earth"; and it was so. **16**Then God made two great [d]lights: the greater light to rule the day, and the lesser light to rule the night. *He made* the stars also. **17**God set them in the firmament of the heavens to give light on the earth, **18**and to rule over the day and over the night, and to divide the light from the darkness. And God saw that *it was good*. **19**So the evening and the morning were the fourth day.

20Then God said, "Let the waters abound with an abundance of living [e]creatures, and let birds fly above the earth across the face of the [f]firmament of the heavens." **21**So God created great sea creatures and every living thing that moves, with which the waters abounded, according to their kind, and every winged bird according to its kind. And God saw that *it was good*. **22**And God blessed them,

saying, “Be fruitful and multiply, and fill the waters in the seas, and let birds multiply on the earth.”
 23 So the evening and the morning were the fifth day.

24 Then God said, “Let the earth bring forth the living creature according to its kind: cattle and creeping thing and beast of the earth, *each* according to its kind”; and it was so. 25 And God made the beast of the earth according to its kind, cattle according to its kind, and everything that creeps on the earth according to its kind. And God saw that *it was good*.

26 Then God said, “Let Us make man in Our image, according to Our likeness; let them have dominion over the fish of the sea, over the birds of the air, and over the cattle, over [g]all the earth and over every creeping thing that creeps on the earth.” 27 So God created man in His *own* image; in the image of God He created him; male and female He created them. 28 Then God blessed them, and God said to them, “Be fruitful and multiply; fill the earth and subdue it; have dominion over the fish of the sea, over the birds of the air, and over every living thing that [h]moves on the earth.”³

The above is an example of a real cosmology, known as Creationism. It is a distillation of much longer cosmological events, recorded in texts such as the Egyptian Book of the Dead, the Coffin Texts, the Enuma Elish, Enki & the World Order, and of course the Rig Veda. It is probably in rongorongo as well, if anyone took the time to use Coelbren to semi-transliterate the text, since Coelbren is a Hebrewesque plasmascript that has some capability to translate ancient Chinese, Etruscan, Hebrew, etc. via plasmaglyphics.⁴

But as a distillation, it covers many of the points which EPEMC has revealed to be accurate. Starting in 1:1 we see the logical issue that Creation is made above something already created: “The Waters.” This only works if “the Waters” is actually a different than assumed meaning, OR literally a reflection of events in the sky off the ocean and lake surfaces. The author has lines of evidence for both.

But Genesis is not a scientific cosmology... most can agree to this. Then why has this been allowed to be proposed by a bishop (LeMaitre), and received the support of a Jewish rock star (Einstein) almost as if the concept of “something from nothing” is scientific?

I say: when the real cosmologies of religions of the world were created, the authors *knew* that everything had already been created, and likely thought of it as “always this way,” and what they really were speaking of was **the creation of more in the sky than their Lord, of language, farming, beer, war, etc.** In the words of the Gilgamesh... “

Gilgamesh, Enki[m]du, and the nether world (line 1-10)

In those days, in those distant days, in those nights, in those remote nights, in those years, in those distant years; in days of yore, when the necessary things had been brought into manifest existence, in days of yore, when the necessary things had been for the first time properly cared for, when bread had been tasted for the first time in the shrines of the Land, when the ovens of the

³ <https://biblehub.com/nkjv/genesis/1.htm>

⁴ https://www.academia.edu/38744706/Uchell_the_High_Lord_and_Shang_Di

Land had been made to work, when the heavens had been separated from the earth, when the earth had been delimited from the heavens, when the fame of mankind had been established.⁵

It may seem impossible, but as has been shown in other papers elsewhere in the author's CV, they meant this **literally**. The Chinese axiom "Heaven is round, and the Earth is square" has played out in earthworks as far as the Ohio River Valley, the Amazon, the British Isles, and in Colombia's newly released 8-mile cliff of rock art.⁶ It was a literal event. Therefore, accretion models are not only mathematically impossible, and thermodynamic bunk⁷ (gases in space do not congeal they spread out, we know this from visiting space), in fact it is the opposite scenario: things are constantly splitting (like mitosis), and forming new material. This material does not "come from nothing into something," that is a metaphor for what mankind experienced when Shamash's plasma double layer (or photosphere) dropped off and many things suddenly appeared in the skies above. See the Egyptian records on Zep Tepi, the "First Time" for more information on this and how the sky was in fact purple at the time.⁸

Meanwhile, BB has nothing at all to say about the formation of the Solar System, hence a reliance on the easily debunked AM, and even less to say on the subjects of biology, consciousness, and other cosmic import. In fact, it eschews any responsibility, and its adherents refuse to recognize that under a typical doppler red-shift ideal, BB is impossible since there is a star "older than the Big Bang." I have news for astronomers, there's trillions to infinite numbers of such stars, however not in our field of vision. It isn't that our section of the universe did not expand from a place, it's that this spreading out is normal, continuous, endless, and in the scheme of an infinite and eternal Universe, unremarkable. It's nothing new, although the re-arrangement may be statistically unique, but as a continuous affair, it is nothing special. Space-time is not the aether, and it isn't even a physical thing, anymore than black holes are. Black holes are just like donut holes... except in space they are pinches and **everything is coming out of them**.

Black Hole Theory (BH) is not BB, but they like to force-fit them into the same one Universe, despite mathematical antipathy towards one another.⁹ Therefore, the fact that standard black holes have been debunked, and really many things "escape" them including plasma, X-rays, radio waves, acoustic waves, magnetism, etc., only helps to undermine the credibility of the SM.

In the remainder of the paper we will step through the various failed promises of BB, identify key failures,¹⁰ and how EPEMC proposes to fix this through a central cosmology and extensions which flow

⁵ <https://lyricstranslate.com/en/gilgamesh-enkidu-and-nether-world-line-1-10-gilgamesh-enkidu-and-nether-world-li.html>

⁶ By the way, archaeologists of the SM are already doing a fine job of misinterpreting that wall. No natives have time to draw 8 miles of pictures about animals, and indeed when you look, there are very few animals, and always at the bottom of the drawings. This reveals natives, like any other civilized people with beliefs in the world, were remarking on cosmological events, - long events that took 8 miles to record - and how they affected and destroyed the Megafauna, again as has been recorded and explained elsewhere in the author's work on Megafauna Extinction.

⁷ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=k0R9S4HFDrg>

⁸ Many cultures, not just China, had no word for blue or green, but instead one single word "blue-green" and red-green and color blindness remains common to this day. However, the best evidence is that trees and plants to this day repel green light, which is the sun's top emission, and grow many times better under purple and UV light. Scientists have noted before with some confusion that as brilliant as photosynthesis is, it is horribly inefficient in normal sunlight. These are lines of evidence and clues to the original nature of our skies. The Egyptians and Chinese had it right to begin with.

⁹ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Y8FsfFs_nvM

¹⁰ The best debunk tables are reserved in the Dark Matter Series papers at https://www.researchgate.net/publication/330897995_The_Dark_Matter_Dine_Dash_Shopping_around_for_answers_Dark_Matter_Scatter_part_2

naturally from a good, Occam's Razor supported, center. One final thing, please note that plasma cosmology may only be as old as BB (1927) but electric-magnetic cosmology pre-dates Newton back to Gilbert's "De Magnete." If Newton had seen Faraday and been able to rely on calculus like Maxwell, he would not have made a gravitation theory but an electrostatic-dynamic model; and this would have led not just to Special Relativity (Poincare), but Einstein would have created General Relativity (GR) using tensor equations with "Maxwell" and we could have avoided all of this mess. Sadly, we rarely make discoveries "in order." Plasma was not even a concept when spectroscopy occurred, and to this day the easily debunked gaseous solar model¹¹ (GS) continues to plague the SM!

Something from "Nothing"

Thermodynamics is a clear, and thus far indisputable scientific theory. That means it is no longer a hypothesis. While not a complete Theory yet, it has five laws¹² which make for "good enough" standards to debunk the SM and GS, to say nothing of debunking GR, BB, and Dark Universe (DU)¹³.

It is unequivocal to say, though, that you cannot create something from nothing. That would include a before and after, and matter and energy. Therefore, on its face, BB falls flat at once. **BB was never even a scientific hypothesis, let alone a cosmology!** It was always a matter of religious zealotry. The choice of BB over plasma cosmology in 1927 due to the rock star status of Einstein (again, the false creator of relativity) marked the end of the Great Enlightenment. Sadly, a plethora of semi-famous eccentrics in Quantum Mechanics, doing real atomic work (and misunderstanding fusion and nearly killing everyone at the Bikini Test because of it), was not able to stop the gushing nonsense of BB, GR, nor BH. Please note that Marklund convection is older than modern black holes, but in the first place Bostick had identified plasmoids as much as ten years earlier than BH theory existed. The marriage of BH to Einstein's purely theoretical Singularity was an unholy alliance of convenience. Not only does the Singularity not describe anything real, quantifiable, or observable, BH theory later divorced it in favor of multiple, nay nearly endless numbers of varying sized black holes..., and the non-physical radii of $R=0$ because "real" physical radii going from (still) the period at the end of this sentence to kilometers in size! All of which are divorced from reality and utility. The only relevant fact is that when you have a Z-pinch, it also does not appear physically, though you see the crushed can, and has a

¹¹ Over 100 lines of evidence refute the GS, and over time with Alven's MHD theorems and HEP in hand, solar astronomers have begun electro-magnifying the plasma sun, remarking how unique it is that gravity generates magnetism. What rubbish, of course, but the mind plays these games when you are within a paradigm, and it is only by stepping out of it, as I did, that you can see the mental tricks. For example, if the sun is held in shape by mutual repulsion of mass gravity vs fusion explosions in the core, then how would matter ever condense into a black hole? If a black hole stays dense forever, how would it ever condense down enough to shatter in a colossal Big Bang? If it does, how would it ever after such a ridiculous explosion return to a collapse in multiple supernovae within microseconds? False! The sun cannot perform work on itself and collapse as a gas into fusion. That's why all fusion experiments are switching to plasma-electric experiments, and stabilizing using radio waves and gamma rays. It takes energy to perform Work, and that energy is transferred via the PEM. The PEM has continually larger and larger sources. Beyond the "center" of the Universe is another larger source, and beyond that, too, etc. But the continuous circulation of energy is due to the "spongy" counter-space which we call space, absorbing lost charge and material and vibration, and reverting it through what the author terms "two way entropy." (TWE) This is part of the concept known as Cosmic Rearrangement Hypothesis (CRH). Note: these are hypotheses at this time, and so not central to this paper or EPEMC at this time. Here mentioned only for completion.

¹² Normal 3, plus a "0th law" and 4th law; see https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Gvr_BcH1Cmw and <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=t8Nm9bnWOTs> for explanations from a world-renowned spectroscopist

¹³ Please note "dark mode" plasma is not DU! This plasma is findable, measurable, and real; it simply does not glow. So dark in the original meaning, not in the pseudoscientific meaning.

varying diameter based upon the amount of current used to generate the magnetic field! The higher the current density, the tighter the pinch, and that is that.

By contrast, in EPEMC nothing is created from nothing and all “somethings” that come from “nothing” have the “nothing” explained.

For example, in his experiments, Bostick showed the galaxy-like plasmoid rotations to be nearly the same as that of real galaxies. The only thing lacking, as we would know now is: a) the cosmic dust which acts (roughly 50% of the missing baryons were found already, and more will be found), b) the small scale magnetics in lab cannot replicate the effects of the AGN, let alone the small scale currents cannot replicate Birkeland Currents, and c) lack of a significant amount of matter to measure the remnant gravitational macro-sized effects. Obviously at that scale, too, he would not necessarily see relativistic effects, but they are present¹⁴.

The source of this “nothing” is unknown at this time, but an aether of a sort (we call it PEM), is expected, and its energetic values have been anticipated for some time. As for the “something” well there is the plasma, the ions, and the flowing charge, which in lab comes from a voltage source but in space comes from higher, larger, and faster moving cores, such as SGR A* and even huge superclusters. See the following figure for how motion of charges and material indicate source and a bi-polar effect of cosmic rearrangement.

Laniakea Supercluster¹⁵

As it happens, processional or relative and absolute velocities increase with size, energy source (voltage), and therefore increase the current speeds, as well. It is speculated that there are even places where the energy is such that the “space-time” is accelerating more rapid than the speed of light, which itself is not constant (depends upon the medium the circuit of energetics is inducting through). However, the author has

¹⁴ Not macro-lensing, which doesn't exist; all lensing is refraction through plasma-electric mediums, such as star atmospheres, nebulae, hidden “dust,” etc.

¹⁵ <https://www.hawaii.edu/news/2020/07/10/laniakea-supercluster-mapping/>
<https://www.nbcnews.com/mach/science/master-plan-universe-revealed-new-galaxy-maps-ncna1040936>

doubts about this claim since the originators have ignored Intrinsic Red Shift and “aged” light factors, which they claim to have debunked yet have not provided any replacement mechanism for the Arp-Conundrum.

While it is nice for the SM to do the “heavy lifting” and aid typical PEM and HEP and condensed matter (CM) research, by first postulating a DU and BB and then debunking themselves while proving PEMC correct, it is perhaps not the most efficient way to go about it. How many accidental discoveries, like superconductivity, have been made which could have been really made and maybe advanced to their perfection of technology in pace with science fiction predictions, *if* there had not been a distraction from real scientific theory because it was **cool** to be different?

“The question which divides us is whether it is crazy enough to have a chance of being correct. My own feeling is that it is not crazy enough.” - Neils Bohr

There’s a special place for intuitives and mystics, like Newton, Tesla, Bohr, etc. but no need for science at that time to throw the baby out with the bathwater! In fact, they just needed to change tubs! Kristian Birkeland was working on auroras (plasma) in 1905 just as Poincare was doing special relativity. If only the internet had existed at the time. But alas, Langmuir was not close to Tesla, nor was Heaviside penpals with Birkeland. So is it any surprise later that Feynman and co. did not work closely with Bostick or Alvfen? If these three had come together, a complete cosmology would have been available to Juergens for his electric sun, and Talbott and Thornhill would not have come so tantalizingly close (but still wrong) with their proto-Saturn solar theory. As they say, “Off by an inch, miss it by a mile.”

Where does the Energy Come From?

Proponents of the GS and BB typically poopoo the Electric Universe by saying “where does the energy come from?” and “Why can’t we see it?” To the latter it’s easy to say back, “we absolutely do,” and cite the Wiley text, “Electric Currents in Geospace and Beyond.” But for some reason no one answers the former with a touche! Why not? Nothing in the GS or BB models account for energy sources. It’s again just conjured up out of nowhere and taken for granted. But thermodynamics denies this. Gases cannot perform Work on themselves, and increase their own temperatures, they cannot congeal, and if the BB started with a Singularity and that was the Everything, including space-time, then there is no incentive to expand, let alone produce heat. In other words, this is another form of God, and not a scientific topic, but a theological one! Furthermore, it would indicate we are still inside the Singularity and that everything we see is merely time stretched out, and we are reading events as if on a phonograph. That makes no sense, and besides, is damn depressing. I reject it!

In PEMC, electricity is generated by the re-arrangement of materials, which induce a magnetic field, which moves charges and material, which again induced magnetic field changes, etc. The source is a continual flow of re-arranging materials. It’s beyond the scope of this paper/OpEd to make speculations about the ultimate results of entropy and motion. Instead, it is sufficient to say the electrical energy that powers the sun comes from the local chimney, and that from larger nebular filaments, generated by the rotation of it all around SGR A*, which as a magnetic pinch is fed by and pushes on the material, and it is - if anything - not a black hole but white hole... in that everything is coming out of SGR A*, and not being pulled in. This has been confirmed when gas bubbles passed by the center and rather than “feeding” upon it, instead SGR A* “burped.”

The Origins of The Earth and Solar System

The Earth, in mythical cosmogonies, rested as a firmament upon things and beneath things. It was flat, and a receptive juncture of heavenly (and hellish) energies. Considering the lack of data for most cultures, this is not a bad arrangement of information. How odd it is that the ancient architects of the Great Pyramid clearly knew the Earth was round, and yet had such a system, right? I maintain that is because they weren't being literal in a spiritual sense, but in a cosmic sense, and the spiritual sciences they practiced were derived from empirical observations (rightly or wrongly). They were not a "death cult" but they witnessed death (of a star, of planets and moons), and births¹⁶, and titanic wars with thunderbolts and plasma streaming (seen often as hanging intestines in the "tree" in many cultures). They saw frightening shapes like wolves, snakes, dragons, and a "mask" of the Lord which horrified, stupefied, and inspired them. Weapons were forged from shapes, and kings based their rights upon plasma glyphs such as the cosmic sceptre, cosmic throne, cosmic pillar, cosmic sword, cosmic trident/halberd, etc. The motions of the bodies were often mesmerizing and confusing, leading to archetypal stories that reflected personal, and Jungian experiences. Memes also were created, and shared, and whence came wise sayings and wise teachings.

In BB, this all just happens purely coincidentally, and yet, is somehow accreting towards a random series of perfections (for life). No means is given to how one rock gets more gold and where irradiated material comes from. It's a continual barrage of explosions (kinetic no less, which spread out and cool down), and mysterious [inexistent] 'dirty snowballs' fill the imagination of fools that ignore the living breathing biosystems of charged spherical shells of the Earth. These shells are not in order of hot to cold in terms of phases of matter, and a mysterious border where life exists on the surface of a solid that turns to gas defines our very right to exist! But there is no explanation for this, or the growth and expansion of bodies, or their uniform behaviors as either spheres or double-lobed rocks.

In BB there is no rhyme or reason, and therefore, no order and no explanation for increasing order in biology or chemistry. There is only chaos and coincidence, and therefore, it is a dead cosmology. It is the true "death cult!"

By contrast, in EPEMC things are related which seem disparate, and yet only if you find the evidence. They are related through a simple underlying principle:

The Unified [Aether] Field theory has been already found and it is the sea of charge in motion we call "Plasma-electromagnetism."¹⁷

The only thing remaining is to 'fully' describe it, if that is possible and the Daoists are wrong about it. Certainly we should not cease our efforts, maybe just augment and balance them, instead of ending them or making toxicity of our efforts.

As for the origins of the Solar System, is is a 6 stage event:

¹⁶ The mechanism for this is still somewhat up for debate between condensed matter physics and plasma or other high energy physics. See: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Pc7_V6p7tcU

¹⁷ In which gravity is the "ashes" of electrical systems, and of charge density, and weak and strong forces and all other EM effects just describe the vagaries of the mystery of this UAF called PEM.

1. Shamash begins to flare and lengthen (as a cosmic egg) as the Sun approaches (possibly with Uranus as Nibiru in tow).¹⁸
2. Shamash splits into Saturn and Jupiter, then Saturn births Neptune, and possibly Jupiter births Uranus, texts are not clear on this part).
3. During the primary 3, a “three body problem emerges” as the solar system swirls around the new sun. At this time, moons shift loyalties and the era of the gods and demigods is in effect, causing manifold stories. The energetic clashes are felt even on the Earth and seen in the sky.
4. The Earth moves from Saturn to Neptune to Jupiter as “Lord” and from there towards the sun, because the Earth is in a terribly erratic motion about Jupiter (at one point our Northern Hemisphere could see the North Pole of Jupiter, as proved without a shadow of doubt by the Allegewi/Hopewell people).¹⁹
5. The Earth flips as it leaves Jupiter’s electric field and enters the sun’s orbit
6. Venus and Mars which had clashed (Venus emerged from inside a dying Saturn and may be its very core) also headed in the same direction as Mercury and Earth. The Earth now has its own real large Jovian moon, and Jupiter has two groups of moons, but also one pro-grade moon within its retrograde. Also Neptune acquires a retrograde moon, which is probably the god Hodr/Hepahaestus. The age of gods ends, and the age of religions about them begins.

Note that this process does not deny the potential for some accretion, but it denies it as a primary process. And indeed, Haumea itself excludes this process, and note its double-lobed behavior. Besides which, we cannot speak of accretion of “gas giants” without discussing liquid metallic hydrogen.. Now that electrical currents and magnetic flux tubes are found throughout the solar system, which ripples with intensity even just outside the Earth’s magnetosphere, we can know that nothing is pure coincidence, that there is an underlying (albeit chaotic like) structure and reason for connections between bodies in the solar system. Working backwards we can answer all sorts of riddles, like...

Credit: NASA²⁰

1. How did Venus come to rotate backwards and why is it slowing down?

¹⁸ <https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1BwWDV9VIYx1pjNulkeNooly-ix4mWTWg1g0z0HUxmPs/edit?usp=sharing>

¹⁹ https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332316290_Hopewellian_Octagons_Proof_that_the_Allegewi_Astronomers_could_see_Jupiter_up_close_Analysis_of_the_Octagon_formations_of_Chillicothe_and_Newark_Earthworks

²⁰ <https://www.nasa.gov/feature/goddard/2018/nasa-spacecraft-discovers-new-magnetic-process-in-turbulent-space>

2. How did the Valles Marinaris and Olympus Mons form?
3. Why is Io so volcanic?
4. Why is Uranus tilted 105 degrees, but Earth and Mars are tilted like Saturn?
5. Why is Earth's water the same isotopes as Saturn's rings²¹ (The diadem of the Lord²²)?
6. Why is Venus so hot? (and why did people think oppositely before, but Velikovsky predicted it?)
7. Why do the gas giants emit more heat than they absorb, and when they do, from water at a higher temperature are they coming down from?
8. Why are Neptune's winds the strongest... and getting stronger?
9. Why are all the atmospheres of the Solar System changing behaviors?
10. Why did Jupiter's south pole add a vortex in 2019?
11. Why is Neptune on a highly elliptical orbit, but other planets are more normal?
12. Why are none of the planets on a disk?
13. Why are they so different?
14. Why are the rocky bodies in the habitable zone instead of the larger gas giants?
15. Why is the sun perfectly round but none of the solar myths show this instead show an egg?
16. Why is it the myths speak of a pole star that is brilliant at night and not during the day, with a crescent revolving on it?
17. Why did Apollo "grow like a baby" as the god was "born"?
18. Why does the moon look Jovian on one side and beaten smooth on the other?
19. Why are Mars' atmospheric components showing up on Venus, as it is Mars that likely had water and life, and not Venus?
20. Where did the Asteroid Belt (and why is it called a belt?) come from?

These questions, and many more do **not** make sense under an accretion and comet-water-extinction model of solar system formation and Earth's geological history. However, they are completely reasonable under a PEMC condition which includes both catastrophism (as a scale of energy and scope) and uniformitarianism (such as tectonics and fluvial erosion). Human history makes far more sense under EPEMC as it includes diffusionism and uniformitarian theories, such as cultural isolation and mutual co-evolution.

The Bible **and** Science can co-exist so long as each finds its proper home and explanations. Really, it's a very clean system that invites more data, and never ignores an OOPArt or line of evidence. Never.

More importantly we no longer have to divorce aborigines from their cultures, and make them choose between a religious semi-reality of long standing tradition, and a dead half-reality which causes moral decay and massive rampant, meaningless consumerism.

This is quite a boon, so what's the catch?

The catch is you have to trust the honesty of the ancient cultures, the innocence and naivety of their beliefs and texts, the reality of their world, and you have to continue to find the evidence because the struggle is real, and ongoing. Yet, with the internet, and despite the destruction of the Allegewi and the Mayan Codices,

²¹ <https://phys.org/news/2018-12-saturn-satellites-earth-moon-phoebe.html>

²² Coffin texts, and "Enki and the World Order"; see this presentation:

https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1QnRXGf1kju3C_CZX06njKK-tnrbGGjq5kOGkRAI-zSM/edit?usp=sharing

and the earthworks, etc. the evidence is coming clearer and clearer, and the results are getting stronger and stronger.

Who or What is in Control?

While it is tempting to say “The Lord” and be done with it, as a religion would, we must first point out that the Lord changed identities depending on the era, and secondly that this is not a scientific answer, per se. One could conclude “the Sun” (son of Thor), is in control, but the fact is that this is skirting away from the real problem: electromagnetism or gravity?

Astronomers, steeped in Relativistic dogma, and not enough history, will maintain that it is primarily gravity that is in control of the Universe. But, realistically, as gravity is 10^{38} times weaker than Electromagnetism, and we now know of a Bessel function means for electricity to cross great distances, while degrading at $1/r^{1/2}$, whereas gravity is degrading by the square of r !²³ As it happens, the weak force has already been merged with electromagnetism²⁴, and many suspect that the strong force is stronger because they are an electron+positron pair in extremely close locked orbit, making a neutron. All three are near to one another in force magnitude. If Newton had known about them, indeed he would have discarded his own theory for the improved model (actually there are several) of electro-gravitics.²⁵ In the future, mankind will discover this mechanism and clarify the matter, once GR is re-worked using tensor equations starting with original SR and electromagnetism.

This isn't the 1920s or 1950s anymore where Einstein and Feynman (et al) were limited by computing power, and Alfvén has already declared in his Nobel acceptance speech that his early work was a failure by ignoring electricity in creating Magnetohydrodynamics. How much longer should we go with these mistakes? NASA and many others are already questioning them, and going back to look at the electromagnetism of black holes (AGN really), and finding indeed they missed much. For every flux tube or “rope” there is an electric current 90 degrees out of phase, but parallel in movement, due to the coaxial and counter-rotating shape that the current takes.²⁶

Think of it this way, what is in control of a car's power, the engine, or a rear wheel? The real power is, of course, in the engine, and is delivered to the wheel. Similarly, gravity is the result of charge motion (literally all quarks and leptons, etc. are measured as masses in electronVolts) consolidation, and the overall dynamics of the flux, divergence, curl, and circuit parameters such as impedance, conductance, capacitance, etc. We measure all of these things using electromagnetism (radio, light, x-ray, fields pressing on atoms for scales, etc.), and determine their properties using thermodynamics, which is IR light, an emf force, etc. So called gravitational lensing has not been observed outside of $R=1$ and is always the result of light passing through/around a star's plasma atmosphere, or through a strongly distorting magnetic pinch (such as an AGN or quasar or magnetar), and at any rate the equations for light in Special Relativity have **literally**

Time Dilation	$T_o = \left[1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2} \right]^{1/2} T$
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Length Contraction	$L = \left[1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2} \right]^{1/2} L_o$
--------------------	--

Relativistic Mass Increase	$m(v) = \left[1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2} \right]^{-1/2} m_o$
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²³ <http://www.ptep-online.com/2015/PP-41-13.PDF>

²⁴ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2405428318300121>

²⁵ This, and many other topics are discussed in more detail and at great length in “The Theory” (2018)

²⁶ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1712.08414.pdf>

nothing to do with gravity in the equations. If you don't believe me, see for yourself at right. These are descriptions of EMF behavior, and that is all.

Truly, the wool has been pulled over the eyes of many astronomers, and they are "hoodwinked"

But General Relativity Has been "Proven"

Setting aside the false proof of M87 as a black hole, when in fact it is nothing of the sort of proof of that, has been covered in other papers, yes, GR has "proven itself." Except that it has been shown that K is variable, and in the first place since the equation for gravity is essentially a special case of the Maxwell equation for the electrostatic force. In reality, a better K could have been assumed to be found doing GR for Maxwell. Since Special Relativity (ala H. Poincare and others before him) was derived using Lorentzian transformations of Maxwell, why was it that Einstein opted (wrongly) for Newton? It was because although he won a Nobel for the Photo-electric Effect, Einstein did not really understand electromagnetism. Not the way Tesla, Steinmetz, and Heaviside did. Also there was more prestige gotten with the Royal Society for utilizing the Newtonian work, because of the classical nature of Newton and various cultural romanticisms in the West. But if Newton had done the work, he would have jumped off of Maxwell or more likely, Heaviside. The Heaviside equations lend themselves particularly well for doing more complex mathematics by starting simply, which is what tensor equations do.

But the only way he could complete the GR work was to divide by 0, and despite warnings from Laplace, Euler, Lorentz, and many other classical mathematicians, this was taken to provide a meaning of "infinity." But $X/0$ is not infinity, it is "not a number" as it is "undefined." Undefined means it is not real. You cannot get something from nothing. Even the Daoists understood this when they said "Real emptiness is not truly empty."

If the philosophers and mathematicians could understand this, how could Einstein and the cult which followed fail at it? "Cult of personality" was incredibly popular in the 20th century²⁷, and even Einstein himself grew weary of it. While Feynman enjoyed a cult status, as did other eccentrics, most of them tried to obey the rules of mathematics and philosophies, and the known laws of physics. Einstein did not. In my opinion he tried to make up for this by attaching his name to the work of Bose, but just think what would have happened if he had a) chosen to go into plasma physics instead of pseudo-astronomy, b) not divided by zero, and c) not put his heft and weight behind G Lemaitre's Big Bang fiasco? What was a joke of physics then found a cult following that has dominated ever since, and wasted a ton of money. Now astronomers think that light is a

²⁷ Do you know that at the time GR came out, and BB, that the mainstream of astronomy thought the Universe was essentially contained in the Milky Way? It was only Edwin Hubble, and later his telescope that was able to challenge the hegemony of the establishment here.

particle²⁸ and pushes on the Voyager spacecraft²⁹ when we know since the 1920s that the solar wind's charge must be causing the "drift" due to the Biefeld-Brown Effect³⁰ (which unduly never won a Nobel Prize³¹).

Invisible Clocks, Dark Universes, and a lot of Other Bunk

Big Bang and GR, doppler red shift, and the like provide for a good load of philosophical imagination, and awkward reading, as well as nifty science fiction debates about surpassing the speed of light. But while SR describes how EMF behaves as it approaches c , it doesn't tell us much about reality. Nor do invisible floating clocks. All of the experiments carried out with atomic clocks have required some corrections even still, because they are electromagnetic experiments being carried out in an electromagnetic environment, in motion, etc. Poincare himself predicted gravity waves, so where is there not to expect a little quantum mechanical "jiggle" due to the Planck limits? What does this have to do with a real cosmology? It is not describing anything really found anywhere. In the cases of dark matter, and dark energy, (and dark photons and negative mass, and negative inertia, etc.) it is literally not found anywhere, because it is all "undefined;" i.e. it is not real.

So in what way do any of these lines of reasoning further the human cause, momentum, etc.? Mankind's major advancements came from connecting to the electric and electronic power, leveraging these to improve mechanical and chemical advantages, and technology, until we were able to turn a Renaissance of art and religion into an Enlightenment that helped us to potentially end worldwide poverty and provide nourishment and sustenance for hundreds of billions of people. With electricity we are able to clothe, farm, feed, travel, and communicate at levels never thought humanly possible before, even with mechanical advantages in the early Industrial era. Meanwhile, gravitics has been useful for satellites, but for little else. Simulating gravitic pressures with lasers (more emf), has never produced fusion reactions. All thermonuclear effects have been regarding electroweak and strong forces, released, and never gravitic. Gravity makes for a good roller coaster, but you still have to put energy into the hill, and actually all of it can be overcome with super magnets, and even improved. With superconductivity, entire touchless rails can be created, and defy gravity both without pushing and despite pull.

3π Möbius track; credit: Royal Institution
(to watch gif, open the Google Doc version)

²⁸ Light cannot be an actual particle (hence $m=0$) only modeled as a particle. Descriptions about why are contained in this paper on pp.9-10 by the author:

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/329629284_Pseudoscience_Cannot_Be_Dark_Matter_A_Short_Concise_Rebuttal_to_Negative_Mass_Dark_Photons_and_the_General_Bunkish_Trend_Physics_in_Crisis_Must_be_Guided_to_Safe_Shores#fullTextFileContent

²⁹ If $m=0$ then $P=0$. Any middle schooler could explain this. Astronomers are very weak in fundamentals, it appears... at least as it pertains to 0.

³⁰

https://www.academia.edu/37439506/Magnetic_Universe_Theory_A_Top_Down_Review_of_Phases_of_Magnetic_Theory_Development_with_accompanying_historiography_and_comparison_with_Unified_Aether_Field_Theories_including_EPEMC

³¹ By then electricity research was passe.

What role does bunk play?

After the failure (and sweeping under the rug) of the Large Hadron Collider to prove Supersymmetry (string theory, etc.) in 2015, it became clear that DU, MOND, SS, etc. were useful in only one regard: because a pseudo-scientific hypothesis cannot be disproven (think: aliens), it can demand unlimited funding. With said unlimited funding, you will eventually find real science. The search for Dark Matter found galaxies without dark matter, cosmic dust, magnetism, cosmic electricity, pulsars with such high pulse rates they could not be spinning, stars darker than charcoal, liquid metallic hydrogen, bose-einstein condensates, electric sheets in space, parallax problems that help define the local chimney, the electric sun, rocky comets, exoplanets gallop, 1.5 trillion more galaxies than previously thought, and a host of other real phenomena! No lambda dark matter, and no dark energy (which they have no idea how to find or prove), but plenty of “exclusion” zones. How useful. Wasteful? Yes, but useful also.

What role would dark photons and negative mass play?

This is a trick question. The answer is none at all. Dark matter theorists (mages?) have already begun calling for “charged” dark matter and so they know they will need to address the 900MHz gorilla in the room, or die on their shield in the continual march of scientific progress. Nothing can stop an idea whose time has come. But in this instance we will not and cannot allow SM to subsume another, better cosmology, and bundle it up like just any other bastard step-child of some half-quack hair-brained professor at a bloated college overfed by grant money from hopeful tech companies and governments. High Energy Physics and Plasma-electromagnetic Cosmologies have no need for DU, BB, SS, and the rest of the failed portions of SM. They’ve made progress in those same Universities, and now that governments and labs are putting up the money, they’re building chambers that can reach the necessary energy levels and temperatures, and achieve voltages and currents that generate all results necessary, without being hamstrung by bunk.

As for a dark photon, by definition you can never see it or find it, so it is recommended to ignore the idea that light can be dark, as it is likely some pseudo-theological atheistic or satanic bent from the dark bowels of despondent academia. But it is not real science.

What EPEMC Does that No Cosmology Does

First it starts with a core which obeys Occam’s Razor and lab science (empirical science), and what nature tells us, without ignoring any data or results. It may demand a rigorous philosophical solution or a critical thinking, but it does not skip results. It might question the results of a paper, if upon reading here are indeed major internal flaws, but it will not refuse raw data.

Then it extends outwards, with testable hypotheses, and takes in data, and seeks naturalized solutions. It looks for explanations for phenomena that are typically ignored, like ball lightning, ghosts, magick, UFOs, OOPArts, strange religious beliefs, medical miracles, spiritual questions, consciousness, etc.

One example is how acupuncture has been ill researched in terms of working mechanisms, because of the ignoring of Electric Fields. By measuring electric fields in a clinic, the author then was able to propose various mechanisms and construct a circuit diagram to describe channel and point behavior which has actual known and measured fMRI and thermographic behaviors, to say nothing of empirical data. By proving the

connection between pain changes and electric field changes (and discluding magnetism, as expected based on failures elsewhere), the author was able to work forward towards an explanation for phenomenology such as “External Wind.”³² But by understanding the phenomena and the mythos, as well as the plasma scripts, it enables the uniquely educated author to create said model based upon the works of others and new data.³³

It is not necessary in this paper to address all the quirky data of the world, and atmospheric mysteries, and mytho-cosmological histories, in order to get the point across that the Extended part of EPEMC piggybacks off a thorough foundation, which itself is both rigorous and ancient.

Again note, too that the above process was able to confirm aspects, and disclude other aspects of theories made previously by the same author, many years before, regarding “scalar magnetic waves.”³⁴ At least in part. More research is needed there, but not to prove the idea that EPEMC has real value, founded in actual science. Moreover, as talked about in a previously mentioned paper “Magnetic Universe Theory” EPEMC does not fall into the polar trap of “electricity only” or “magnetism only” or “plasma only”, and certainly not into a gravity well of bunkular nonsense!

Big Bang Doesn't Free Mankind

Setting aside nihilistic solipsism which cannot really be eradicated (due to the polarity of truth), it is well known in psychology that positive formulations and (in essence) hope created more positive biological results for individuals. This probably does resemble some larger Universal truth, but let us take it for granted that good health is better than bad health (mind, body, spirit, etc.). As it is so, then Science, as a whole, should yield results, purpose, Vision, and aid a person let alone a society in finding where it belongs, and freeing it to empower itself and reach the grandest heights or be at peace in the middle-lows, alike.

While every cosmology in world history (except BB) has given people some sense of personal scale and relation to the divine, as well as a religious or spiritual purpose, or latitude to do what they like, only EPEMC has thus far given them both validation and ultimate freedom to pursue the greatest heights by removing the shackles of guilt (leastways as far as the ancient catastrophes and foundations of religion are concerned), and on top of that :

- ❖ **Encouraged furthering personal and social empowerment via harnessing the direct sources of energy such as space electricity and even the “aether” (sea of charges), and to see the entire Earth as a useful energetic zone.**
- ❖ **Freed mankind of fear of approaching the speed of light without “cheats” such as theoretical wormholes, etc. and disregarding black holes as a gravitic threat but instead to harness as useful sources of energetics.**

Nothing is completely free of responsibility, though, primarily to the laws of physics and chemistry, and so there are warnings and limitations, particularly regarding space travel and radiation, of economics (as it

³²

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/328697566_Clinical_Electric_Field_Measurements_In_situ_pre_and_post_treatment_measurement_data_with_weather_and_space-weather_lunar_and_solar_data_with_self-reported_pain_and_significance_scales_in_three_phases

³³

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/330117614_Charge_Distribution_Networks_CDN_as_Meridians_Utilizing_conductivity_as_replacement_structure_for_meridians_comparison_with_neural_muscular_and_fascial_models

³⁴ https://www.academia.edu/8547496/Scalar_Magnetic_Waves_and_Qi_a_first_draft_of_a_hypothesis

reflects the concepts of flux and capacitance, and draws its source from individual's metabolic efforts). But otherwise EPEMC gives what even alien architect "cosmology" cannot give: a bedrock of data that honors aboriginal testimony, archaeological research, and yet removes the fear of displeasing a Lord (unless one takes and keeps a faith, for other reasons), as the Lord is clearly Saturnian and the tradition of passing lordship between "solar" bodies. If you do not currently worship Sol, the Sun, then you have already denied this tradition. So why adhere to the limits created by them? Instead be a moral humanist, be egalitarian, and nothing else unless you desire to be.

A faith in, for example, a Yeshua Christ does not negate any of this research, and so it is your own personal desire. Therefore, choose a cosmology that both empowers you (literally) by encouraging connection to what is now demonstrably the PEM force in action, and frees you to research and search the shores of human history, world history, the future, modern issues (and whence they come), as well as distant lands and worlds. A dead cosmology in crisis will not take you to any of these places, even if you declare yourself to know the impossible, such as what happened at the very moments just before and after the supposed Big Bang. Hubris has never helped anyone, and it has harmed mankind greatly.

Conclusion

EPEMC is a vastly superior cosmology for many enumerated reasons. First it has older roots, indeed even to the most ancient of days of mankind's studies and engineering, second it is rooted in empirical science and not mathemagic and Dark Universes made out of convenience and fairy dust. Finally, it describes not only what we can see but implores to explore what may be there which we have not yet seen but definitely could see if we tried. It frees mankind from shackles of the past, and asks/demands for accountability for the present, while encouraging a better future. It respects religious differences, even explains them, but does not seek to disrespect them or be at conflict or tension with them, and introduce ludicrous concepts like "dark photons" in order to explain what is happening right around us. It is, as a cosmology, everything Big Bang is not and never could be, because it doesn't start from a half-truth and proceed inexorably to wrong conclusions.

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